

O‘ZBEKISTONDAGI OLIY TA’LIM MUASSASALARINING IQTISODIY BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida xizmatlar sohasini takomillashtirish orqali barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash, muammo va yechimlari haqida fikrlar keltirilgan. Hozirgi rivojlanayotgan davrda mablag'lar sohaga to'g'ri yo'naltirilmasa, mablag'lar aylanishi innovatsion yechimlar orqali boshqarilmasa, mablag'larning sarflanishi kutilgan samarani bermaydi. Maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalari tomonidan ko'rsatilayotgan xizmatlardan tushadigan tushumlarni innovatsion yechimlar orqali boshqarish, amaldagi me'yoriy hujjatlardagi kamchiliklar, ularni takomillashtirishning ahamiyati to'g'risida takliflar keltirilgan.

KALIT SO‘ZLAR

innovatsion yondashuv, iqtisodiy o'sish, mablag'lar, ta'lim xizmatlari, imtiyozlar, kadrlar, iqtisodiy tahlil.

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены идеи о проблемах и решениях обеспечения устойчивого экономического роста за счет совершенствования сферы услуг в высших учебных заведениях. В текущий развивающийся период, если средства не будут должным образом направлены в отрасль, если обращение средств не будет управляться посредством инновационных решений, расходование средств не даст ожидаемого эффекта. В статье представлены предложения по управлению доходами от услуг, оказываемых высшими учебными заведениями, посредством инновационных решений, недостатки действующих нормативных документов и важность их совершенствования.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

инновационный подход, экономический рост, средства, образовательные услуги, льготы, кадры, экономический анализ.

OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE ECONOMIC SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article presents ideas about the problems and solutions of ensuring sustainable economic growth by improving the service sector in higher education institutions. In the current developing period, if the funds are not properly directed to the sector, if the circulation of funds is not managed through innovative solutions, the spending of funds will not give the expected effect. The article presents proposals on the management of revenues from services provided by higher education institutions through innovative solutions, shortcomings in the current regulatory documents, and the importance of their improvement.

KEYWORDS

innovative approach, economic growth, funds, educational services, benefits, personnel, economic analysis

The main activity of higher education institutions is to provide all sectors of the country with qualified personnel. Economic activity, in turn, is mainly supported through the revenues generated from the provision of services. Nowadays, in training highly qualified personnel that meet modern requirements, the scientific, pedagogical, and economic potential of higher education institutions plays an important role. The current competition among higher education institutions is related to the level of economic capacity, which determines their ability to retain personnel with high scientific and pedagogical potential. This is because the demand for qualified personnel by higher education institutions requires offering them higher monthly salaries—directing a significant portion of financial resources to their wages, providing various benefits, and creating adequate modern working conditions for their activities. All of these are assessed by the results of developing innovative solutions in correctly pricing services and efficiently using existing economic and material resources.

According to Presidential Decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-60 dated December 24, 2021, “On Additional Measures to Ensure the Academic and Organizational-Administrative Independence of State Higher Education Institutions” and No. PQ-61 “On Measures to Grant Financial Independence to State Higher Education Institutions,” a number of higher education institutions have been granted extensive powers in the fields of academic and organizational management. In particular, the Supervisory Boards of higher education institutions have been given the authority to make decisions related to the development of the institution and its financial activities. Using these powers, Supervisory Boards may apply innovative approaches in independently

determining the movement of funds, and such approaches may also be proposed by the institutions themselves to the Supervisory Boards as initiatives. These types of proposals are necessarily formed on the basis of economic analysis.

A study was conducted on the payment of tuition fees (contract-based payments) over the past three years at higher education institutions located in the Samarkand region. The analysis revealed that, on average, 40–42 percent of tuition fees are paid near the end of the academic year, mainly due to extended payment deadlines. Considering that nearly 99 percent of the revenue generated by higher education institutions from educational services comes from tuition fees, it is evident that a significant portion of the income is received during the second half of the academic year. One of the main reasons for the delay in tuition payments is, firstly, that higher education institutions have been regularly extending payment deadlines in recent years; secondly, it is related to the population’s ability to pay. The damage caused by delayed payments negatively affects the financial stability of higher education institutions. That is, although the tuition fees do not increase throughout the year, the rise in salaries and equivalent payments, utility and other service costs, as well as the prices of other material assets, leads to a situation where some of the expenses planned at the beginning of the year cannot be implemented, or some of the institution’s intended goals may not be achieved. **How can this situation be resolved?**

First of all, the Boards of Trustees of higher education institutions should consider providing incentives to students who pay the full amount of their tuition fees at the beginning of the academic year. These incentives may include: providing accommodation, free meals at the student cafeteria,

offering a certain discount on the tuition fee, preferential access to other services provided by the higher education institution, and so on. Let us now consider the advantages of offering a certain discount on the tuition fee.

By the decision of the Board of Trustees, a 10% discount may be applied to students who pay the full amount of their tuition fee in one payment at the beginning of the academic year. Firstly, due to inflation throughout the year, the value of tuition fees that are paid in installments during the second half of the academic year — due to extended payment deadlines — continues to decrease. That is, the purchasing power of these delayed payments gradually diminishes over time. Secondly, the lump-sum tuition payments made at the beginning of the academic year can be deposited in banks, and the current interest rates on deposits (which average between 16–20% today) will compensate for both the discount granted on the tuition and the effects of inflation.

This approach creates mutual benefits for both parties:

- Students receive a financial privilege when paying tuition fees;
- Higher education institutions gain additional income and economic stability.

Aligning the benefits granted to students in paying tuition fees with the population’s actual payment capacity is also considered an important economic solution. For example, a certain product or service owned by the population — which has material value — may generate added value over time. A student might plan to fully cover their tuition fee based on the added value that will be generated in the future. However, rather than waiting for this future-added value to materialize, allowing the student to deduct its projected value from the tuition fee today brings them direct financial convenience. That is, it is more beneficial for the payer to receive a discount now, rather than rely on potential income that may be earned after a period of time. For instance, in the currently high-demand field of Jurisprudence, the minimum tuition fee per academic year for one student is 11,250,000 UZS, while the differentiated tuition fee can reach up to 213,750,000 UZS (i.e., 19 times the base amount). A 10% discount on this amount would equal 21,375,000 UZS, which is the financial privilege extended to the population. The remaining 192,375,000 UZS could be deposited in commercial banks. Given today’s average deposit interest rates, the expected income from such a deposit would be approximately 37,000,000 UZS. As seen from this, while 21,375,000 UZS is granted as a discount to the student, the higher education institution would still

gain a net profit of 15,625,000 UZS after covering the discount amount through the earned interest.

In conclusion, granting higher education institutions and their Boards of Trustees the authority to provide economically and materially justified benefits, as well as easing centralized management by delegating specific powers in particular areas, will undoubtedly contribute to the sustainable economic growth of higher education institutions.

REFERENCES

1. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-60 dated December 24, 2021, “*On additional measures to ensure academic and organizational-management independence of state higher education institutions.*”
2. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-61 dated December 24, 2021, “*On measures to provide financial independence to state higher education institutions.*”
3. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4391 dated July 11, 2019, “*On measures to introduce new principles of governance in the system of higher and secondary specialized education.*”
4. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5763 dated July 11, 2019, “*On measures for reforming governance in the field of higher and secondary specialized education.*”
5. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 967 dated December 3, 2019, “*On the gradual transition of higher education institutions to a self-financing system.*”